

Interactive Communication Competencies for Special Learners: Receptive Learning Activities

Jean S. Dabaso¹, Renato A. Dabaso²

¹College President, Carcar City College, Carcar City Cebu, Philippines

²Administrative Assistant III, Department of Education- Carcar City Division, Carcar City Cebu, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15591805>

Published Date: 04-June-2025

Abstract: This investigation was focused on the interactive communication competencies of the children with Autism. These special children use the language specifically the syntax, semantic and pragmatic in the course of conversation and other situations like games, peer group activity and solving conflicts. The relationship between interactive communication competencies and socioeconomic status of children with autism of Special Education Center of Carcar City Central Elementary School was determined through descriptive quantitative research particularly the use of Chi-square of Independence. Findings revealed that critical tabled chi-square (82.45) is greater than the computed chi-square (51.58). This implied that there was no enough evidence to show that the socioeconomic status has bearing on the children's competencies. As the relationship between interactive communication competencies and socioeconomic status of the subjects, there was no significant relationship between under studied variables.

Keywords: Autism, Special Education, Interactive Communication, Special Learners, Descriptive Research, Carcar City, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language is considered as the most effective medium of communication. People use language in both oral and written communication. Oral communication, for example, requires attentiveness, focus and understanding of the words throughout the conversation (Montañez, 2015).

The implications for studying language and other Communication Arts subjects across disciplines are reflected in the provisions of the lawful commands and policies depicted in the Department of Education (DepEd) Orders and the Constitution. Dañuop (2010) said that directives, for example, evidently seek to respond to DepEd's vision for giving discrimination-free quality education for Filipino children both typical and with special needs like children with autism.

The World Health Organization (2013) defines Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) as a group of complex brain development disorders. These disorders, such as autism, childhood disintegrative disorder and Asperger syndrome, are characterized by difficulties in social communication and interaction and a restricted and repetitive repertoire of interests and activities.

Recent review of the World Health Organization (2013) the estimated global prevalence is 62/10,000. Based on the study of the Research in Development Disabilities, the most recent reported prevalence of the Autism Spectrum Condition in the United States was 1 in 68 (CDC, 2014). Although, diagnostic instruments and screening facilities of ASD children are mostly available to private doctor practitioners, parents are submitting their children for examination.

Another study within the same premise was that of Zalenski et al, cited in the work of Research Development Disabilities (2014), that early intervention is commendable because this can lead to better result. Parent's support plays an important role in the development of child's respective understanding and social communication and interaction skills. Children with ASD need love from the people within and outside families. Due to child's behavioral condition, family members must extend care and support to their children in a daily basis.

The researcher conducted this investigation to determine the level of the interactive communication competencies of the children with Autism of the SPED class of Carcar City Division.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the descriptive quantitative method of gathering data. This statistical method was used to summarize data numerically and or graphically. Chi-square of Independence was used to show the significant relationship between socioeconomic status of the parents and the social communication and interaction competencies of the children with autism. The respondents were the parents of the children with autism while the subjects were the nine (9) children with ASD. The respondents as well as the subjects were chosen using the universal sampling techniques. The data from the respondents and subjects were gathered using profiling sheet. The researcher's sheet were reproduced and distributed to the respondents. With this, the gathered data and other relevant facts were presented in a simpler manner and by categories plus their corresponding frequencies containing the numbers of observation in which the proponent and its end users have easier grasp of the information therein.

For this investigation, two research instruments were used. Part 1 was the profiling sheet to get the profile of children with autism as well as their respective parents. This was an adapted instrument from Mier (2014). Part 2 was an adapted tool from PIP Developmental Chart, and it was modified to get the other necessary data. This tool was used to gather information on the competencies of the children with autism. It is composed of social, communication and interaction exercises in the different situations that gave the learners opportunities to socialize and expose themselves to others. In this manner, the children with autism hope to have meaningful experience and develop self-confidence and, later on, critical thinking.

Permission was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent, Carcar City Division, parents and from other persons and offices concerned to allow or conduct the investigation of the level of interactive communication competencies of children with Autism of Carcar City Elementary School SPED Center.

The facilitation of the instrument for the subjects was done by the teacher in-charge. The researcher or teacher evaluator gave the observation by indicating the specified letter scale (A, O, S, N). The researcher used Mastered, Developing, Approaching and No Notation to describe the competencies of the children with unique characteristics.

On the other hand, the data from the respondents and subjects were gathered using profiling sheet. The researcher's sheet was reproduced and distributed to the respondents. Examination and analysis were done after gathering the said data. The responses were tallied to get the raw data to be treated statistically to generate empirical data. Interpretation and analysis of the data were reflected in each matrix that answered the specific questions of the study.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section encloses the results of each domain which includes the attending skills, self-awareness, self at play, self at work, inappropriate social behavior, listening or receptive language skills, expressive language skills and auditory perception of the children with Autism Spectrum Disorder of DepEd- Carcar City Division.

A. Profile of the Subjects

The profiles of the subjects were determined as to the biological age, gender, number of years in the SPED class and socioeconomic status of the parents of the children with Autism of Carcar City Central Elementary School Special Education Center during the school year 2015-2016. The profile as to age and gender were determined using the frequency and simple percentage. Table 2 shows the age and gender of the subject.

TABLE I: BIOLOGICAL AGE AND GENDER PROFILE OF THE SUBJECTS

Biological Age	Gender		Total
	M	F	
25 and above	0	0	0
18-24	1		1
11-17	3	1	4
3-10	4		4
Totality	8	1	9
Mean Biological Age	12		

As revealed in Table 2, out of 9 pupils in Carcar City Central Elementary School SPED Center, 4 pupils are belonged 3 to 10 years old. There are also 4 children whose age is between 11-17 years old and there is only one pupil whose age belonged to 18-24 years old. Majority of the age of the subjects' ranges from 3 to 17 years old but the average age of these children is 12 years old.

A twelve (12) year old child is generally regarded to be in an adolescence stage (Albarracin, 2014). In Havighurst's developmental tasks during the life span of a normal individual, the children are now into describing, accepting and achieving socially responsible behavior. Moreover, they are already acquiring a set of values and an ethical system as a guide to behavior-developing an ideology. However, the children with ASD are unique because they have delays and deficits in understanding. They believe that everyone does and supposes just the way they do (Baron-Cohen, 2009).

Table 2 also shows the gender profile of the subjects. Out of 9 pupils of Carcar City Elementary School SPED Center, 8 or 89% are males while one (1) or 11% is a female. The findings of this study tell that the 8:1 gender ratio between boys and girls shows a predominance of ASD in boys.

Totality in Table 2 illustrates that there are more males than female subjects. This study agrees with the report conducted by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) that autism is five times more common among boys than girls (CDC, 2014).

Moreover, results also conform the findings of the investigation conducted by the Research Development Disabilities (2014) that there was higher prevalence of Autism Spectrum Condition in boys compared to girls by 27.6 times higher (Sun, 2014).

TABLE II: NUMBER OF YEARS IN THE SPED CENTER

Age	Less than 1 year				1-3				4-6				7-10				More than 10 years			
	F		%		F		%		f		%		f		%		f		%	
25 and above	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18-24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	11	0	0
11-17	0	0	0	0	2	22	2	22	2	22	2	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3-10	1	11	0	0	1	11	2	22	2	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Totally	1	11	0	0	3	33	4	44	1	11	1	11	1	11	1	11	1	11	1	11

Table 2 reveals that one (1) or 11% out 9 pupils of Carcar City Elementary School SPED Center studied at the center for less than a year. There are four (4) children with Autism or 44% who have been enrolled in the special class for 1-3 years already. There are three (3) challenged pupils or 33% who are staying for 4-6 years now while there is one (1) pupil or 11% who attended special classes for more than 10 years.

As indicated in Table 3, there is germane information about educational intervention of children with ASD. This divulges that there is continuous intervention for the children with autism. Figures tell that there is an interest in early and persistent intervention that believe for ASD to lead to more optimal outcomes (Durocher, 2010).

Furthermore, according to Chaban (2010), online columnist of Learning and Education particularly the About Kids Health, that it is necessary to be reminded that the children with unique characteristics are not only learning but they are swiftly improving over their 12 years in school. Chaban added that these developments comprise physical, social, emotional and mental development.

TABLE III: OCCUPATION OF PARENTS

Occupation	f	%
Business	1	11
Laundering	2	22
Construction Worker	2	22
Others:		
Livestock	1	11
Employee	3	33
Totally	9	100

Table 4 shows that out of 9 parents, one (1) or 11% ventures into business. There are two (2) or 22% who engage to laundering, two (2) or 22% work as construction workers, while one (1) or 11% explores the livestock production. Most parents are employees of different sectors of the society which corresponds to three (3) or 33%.

According to Dickerson et al (2014), parental occupation is jointly associated with severity and diagnosis of children with autism. Researchers added that identification of parents who have children with unique characteristics could be of help for earlier identification and diagnosis of their children which will lead to earlier intervention and better outcomes of these challenged individuals.

TABLE IV: EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	f	%	f	%
College Graduate	3	33	2	22
College Level	1	11	0	0
High School Graduate	1	11	2	22
High School Level	2	22	2	22
Elementary	2	22	1	11
<i>*Children without a father</i>			2	22

As shown in Table 4, out of 9 mothers three (3) or 33 % graduated in college, one (1) or 11% reached college but did not graduate, one (1) or 11% finished high school, two (2) or 22% who made it to high school level, while two (2) or 22% graduated elementary.

It is also presented in Table 5 that out of 9 fathers, two (2) or 22% graduated in college, two (2) or 22% also reached high school level, two (2) or 22% finished high school while one (1) or 11% graduated elementary. This also shows that there are two (2) children with autism or 22% have no father.

In a research conducted by Xiang Sun et al (2014), parent's educational attainment was associated to parental concerns. Based on the result of the study, parents with higher academic attainment reported higher levels of concern. Continuous intervention and education, for example, were undergone to show concerns, care and love for the children.

On the other hand, in the research conducted by Kidd et al (2010) of Curtin University of Technology and Elizabeth Kaczmarek of Edith Cowan University stated that parents are turning to an alternative teaching approach particularly the home education. However, family background, economic status, educational background, and prior professional experience were taken into consideration.

TABLE V: AVAILABILITY OF READING MATERIALS AT HOME

Availability of Reading Materials at	WM	Interpretation
1.textbook	1.78	Adequate
2.magazine	1.89	Adequate
3.storybook	1.56	Less Adequate
4.pocketbook	1.33	Less Adequate
5.novel	1.11	Less Adequate
6.encyclopedia	1.44	Less Adequate
7.periodicals	1.44	Less Adequate
8.newspaper	1.78	Adequate
9.readers' digest	1.22	Less Adequate
10.journal	1.33	Less Adequate
11.article	1.33	Less Adequate
12.dictionary	1.44	Less Adequate
13. online reading materials	1.78	Adequate

References: **Very Adequate** - when the available reading materials reach above 10;

Adequate - when the available reading materials reach 6-9;

Less Adequate - when the available reading materials reach 5 and below.

As illustrated in Table 5, magazine has a weighted mean of 1.89 which implies adequacy of numbers of reading materials at home while novel ranks the last with 1.11 weighted mean. Result shows that the reading materials found in the respective home of the children with Autism are **less adequate** with an equivalent weighted mean of 1.5. This signifies that the available reading materials reached 5 and below.

Research shows that reading to children encourages the youngsters to read on their own. Having a library of 500 books at home provides an educational advantage over the learners who do not have the facility at home. Moreover, numerous availability of books at home reflect family's "scholarly culture" which is the family's way of life (Essex Library Association, 2010).

The Children's Literacy Network posted the research conducted by the University of Tennessee, Knoxville that it is not enough to merely give the children the access to library but it is vital to provide access to books in their respective home. Researcher added that said undertaking leads to the most opportunities of children to read more and more (Children's Literacy Network, 2012).

TABLE VI: FAMILY'S FINANCIAL STATUS

Family Financial Status	<i>f</i>	%
30,001 and above	2	22
20,001 - 30,000	0	0
10,001 - 20,000	1	11
7,001 - 10,000	0	0
Less than 7,000	6	67

As illustrated in Table 6, the monthly income of the parents of the children with ASD usually ranges from less than Php 7,000.00. This component garners the highest percentage which is six (6) or 67%, the monthly income amounting to Php 30,001 and above comes second getting two (2) or 22% followed by the amount of Php 10,001 to 20,000.00 which is one (1) or 11%.

The National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) said that in order for a family of five (5) to stay out from poverty, the family should have an average income of around Php 7,768.80 per month or Php 93,225.60 per year (NEDA, 2013).

Citing in Rappler, an online news site, NEDA Director General Arsenio Balisacan, the family should earn an estimate of Php 258.96 per day. This was the amount a household must have to purchase food, water and clothing for a-day consumption (Balisacan, 2013).

Studies have shown that family financial status is sizeable especially autism diagnosis is concerned. According to Bearman (2011), children whose parents had fewer economic resources simply weren't diagnosed as often as wealthier children.

The results of the study also concur with Republic Act 992 series of 2013 that autism still remains in the marginalized sector of the country. Thus, the government must continuously find ways to augment the status of the family whose children afflicted with this disorder. In addition, according to the Children's Literary Network (2012) that family financial status or the income levels of the parents were less important in determining the future success.

B. Levels of Social Communication and Interaction Competencies

This section explains the result of each domain which includes the attending skills, self-awareness, self at play, self at work, inappropriate social behavior, listening or receptive language skills, expressive language skills and auditory perception. It utilizes the PIP Developmental Chart to determine the level of the social interaction and communication competencies of the children with autism.

TABLE VII: ATTENDING SKILLS

BASIC COMPETENCIES	WM	Description
<i>A. Attending Skills</i>		
<i>1. Body Contact (with prodding /prompting)</i>		
<i>1.1 Makes eye contact in response to name</i>	3.33	<i>Mastered</i>

<i>1.2 Looks at the person facing him when giving the following instructions:</i>		
1.2.1 "Look at me"	3.56	Mastered
1.2.2 "Wash your hands"	3.00	Developing
1.2.3 "Get the soap"	3.11	Developing
1.2.4 "Turn on/off the faucet"	2.88	Developing
<i>1.3 Makes response to instruction by:</i>		
1.3.1 smiling	2.56	Developing
1.3.2 laughing	3.00	Developing
1.3.3 frowning	1.78	Approaching
1.3.4 nodding	2.56	Developing
1.3.5 Waving the hands	2.78	Developing
1.3.6 Directly performing the task	3.33	Mastered
2. Attention Span - Tactile (with maximum assistance)		
<i>2.1 Attempts to take the task (s)/ material (s) for manipulation for at least five (5) minutes</i>		
2.1.1 "Copy a line"	2.78	Developing
2.1.2 "Draw a circle"	2.89	Developing
2.1.3 "Start scribbling"	3.00	Developing
<i>2.2 Manipulates task(s)/ material(s) presented without completion</i>		
2.2.1 "Copy a line"	2.22	Approaching
2.2.2 "Draw a circle"	2.33	Approaching
2.2.3 "Start scribbling"	2.33	Approaching
2.3 Returns material (s) used	2.56	Developing
3. Attention Span – Auditory (with prompting)		
3.1 Moves ahead to locate sound (s)	3.11	Developing
3.2 Sits for at least 5 minutes to listen to the sound	3.67	Mastered
<i>3.3 Imitates the sound with verbal prompting from an audit</i>		
3.3.1 Sings ABCDE...	2.89	Developing
3.3.2 Rings a bell purposefully	2.67	Developing
3.3.3 Imitates sticking tongue out	2.67	Developing
3.3.4 Imitates dialogue from the sounds or video clip	2.78	Developing
Totally	2.82	Developing

Table 7 shows the three (3) categories under **Attending Skills**, namely: Body Contact, Attention Span – Tactile, and Attention Span – Auditory.

This demonstrates that among the instructions given under **Body Contact**, "look at me" ranks first with a weighted of 3.56 and the two (2) categories "rings a bell purposefully and imitates sticking tongue out" acquire a comparable weighted mean of 2.67 ranks last.

Results for Attending Skills garner the weighted mean of 2.82. This means that children with Autism are on the **developing level of competence**. This signifies that the subject has executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

According to Stokes (2011), Autism Consultant, those there common features of children with Autism which one of these is difficulty of interpreting data? As a result, children can demonstrate variable attending skills depending upon the child's interest.

TABLE VIII: SELF-AWARENESS

<i>B. Self-awareness</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Express emotions through body language like:		
1.1 smiling	3.11	Developing
1.2 clapping	2.78	Developing
1.3 singing	2.89	Developing
1.4 dancing	2.78	Developing
1.5 whining	4	Mastered
2. Expresses common emotions such as:		
2.1 happy	3.22	Developing
2.2 angry	2.44	Approaching
2.3 sad	2.33	Approaching
3. Verbalizes own name through imitations or when told to:		
3.1 "My name is _____"	2.5	Developing
4. Tells own age with the use either of the following:		
4.1 sticks	1.44	No Notation
4.2 stones	1.56	No Notation
4.3 fingers	2.67	Developing
5. Asked personal objects / things by:	1.89	Approaching
5.1 book	2.67	Developing
5.2 pencil	2.56	Developing
5.3 crayon	2.56	Developing
5.4 bag	2.56	Developing
5.5 ball or doll	2.67	Developing
6. Identifies the members of the family like:		
6.1 father	3.44	Mastered
6.2 mother	3.44	Mastered
6.3 brother. Sister	3.56	Mastered
6.4 guardian	3.56	Mastered
7. identifies the major parts of the body like:		
7.1 nose	3.22	Developing
7.2 eyes	3.11	Developing
7.3 ears	3	Developing
7.4 mouth	3	Developing
7.5 teeth	3	Developing
8. identifies the major parts of the body through:		
8.1 nose	3.11	Developing
8.2 eyes	3.11	Developing
8.3 ears	3	Developing
8.4 mouth	3	Developing
8.5 teeth	3	Developing
9. Asks permissions to use things that belong to others	2.22	Approaching
10. Knows gender identity	2.22	Approaching
11. appreciates other's good behavior by saying:		
11.1 Good job!	2.22	Approaching
11.2 Very Good!	2.44	Approaching
11.3 Thank you!	2.78	Developing
WM	2.79	

Table 8 shows that children with Autism express emotions through body language like whining which has the highest weighted mean of 4.00 and clapping and dancing which is the lowest has comparable weighted mean of 2.78. Average mean

for this sub-category of 3.11 which tells that children with Autism are at the **developing level** of competencies. This means that the subject has executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

The second sub-class expresses common emotions such as happy, angry and sad. Facts reveal that happy with a weighted mean of 3.22 ranks first in this sub-category and sad ranks last with an average mean of 2.33. This sub-category garners 2.67 which mean the children with Autism are at the **developing level** of competencies which means the subject has executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

The third sub-group shows that children with Autism are the **developing level** of competency with regards to verbalizing own name through imitations with weight mean of 2.50.

Results of the fourth sub-questions imply that children with Autism tell own age by using fingers which has the highest weighted mean of 2.67, and by using sticks with weighted mean of 1.44 is the last. Facts of this sub-grouping garner an average mean of 1.89 which means children with ASD are at the **approaching level**. The subject has occasionally executed or performed the given social activities with or without prodding.

Along with the fifth and sixth sub-groupings, verbalizes ages when asked garners 1.89 while naming personal objects or things such as book, pencil, crayon, bag and ball or doll by pointing, showing and bringing the objects to the teacher has weighted mean of 2.60. This signifies that children's level of competencies is at the approaching level which means subject has occasionally executed or performed the given social activities with or without prodding.

The seventh sub-class talks about identification the members of the family; brother, sister and guardian have an analogous weighted mean of 3.56 while father and mother have similar weighted mean of 3.44. Facts say that children at the **mastered level** as far as identification of family members are concerned and they have executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

The eighth and ninth sub-categories are the identification of the major parts of the body such as nose, eyes, ears, mouth and teeth. Verbal identification gets 3.07 weighted mean while identifying the major body through illustration garners weighted mean of 3.04. These two (2) sub-categories imply that children have **mastered** these competencies. The subject has executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

The last three categories reveal ASD children ask permissions to use things that belong to others and know gender identity have equal weighted mean of 2.22. Children while children appreciate other's good behavior by saying good job, very good and thank you, garners weighted mean of 2.48. This signifies children's competencies are at **approaching level**. The subject has occasionally executed or performed the given social activities with or without prodding.

These findings are supported by Lyons and Fitzgerald (2013) when they said that the child's capability to know or identify one's own face in the mirror is well thought-out an ordeal for "self-awareness. The researchers added that the aptitude to distinguish one-self to other is very important for the development of self-awareness.

TABLE IX: Self at Play (Play and Group Participation Skills)

<i>C. Self at play (Play and Group Participation Skills)</i>	WM	Description
1. Comes to school with a pleasant disposition by greeting teachers, visitors through body language, signs, and verbal language like:		
1.1 Good morning!	2.89	Developing
1.2 Hi! Hello!	2.11	Approaching
1.3 Bye!	3.11	Developing
Others: please specify		
2. Plays harmoniously with others during a cooperative activity with complete supervision e.g. hide and seek etc.	2.56	Developing
3. Borrows play thing(s) politely	2.22	Approaching

4. Uses the following expressions with physical or verbal guidance whenever necessary or through gestures and showing a flashcard/chart.		
4.1 “Thank you!”	2.38	Approaching
4.2 “Please”	1.78	Approaching
4.3 “May I _____”	1.44	No Notation
Others: please specify		
5. Initiates social interaction with another child like sharing toys	2.11	Approaching
6. Joins in play with one other person chasing or kicking a ball	2.22	Approaching
7. Enjoys being swung, lifted etc. in play	2.00	Approaching
8. Enjoys peek-a-boo	1.78	Approaching
9. Has several friends, may have one special friend	2.33	Approaching
10. Pats and smiles at own reflection in mirror	3.44	Mastered
11. Expresses verbal directions in play activities	2.89	Developing
12. Takes turns in play without adult facilitation	3.33	Mastered
13. Plays cooperatively with 2/3 others for 20 minutes	2.44	Approaching
Totality	2.41	Approaching

As revealed in Table 9, pats and smiles at own reflection in mirror has the highest weighted mean of 3.44, and enjoys peek-a-boo with weighted mean of 1.78 is the lowest. The children’s competencies with regards to self-at-play garners total weighted mean of 2.68 or **approaching level**. This means the subject has occasionally executed or performed the given social activities with or without prodding and prompting.

According to Raising Children Network (2016), play affects how children with autism develop language, communication and social skills. There are several types of play which parents can variedly explore. For example, exploratory play, cause and effect play and toy play are some of the plays that can be administered to children with autism.

TABLE X: Self at Work

<i>D. Self at Work</i>	WM	Description
1. Works on cooperative activities harmoniously without constant supervision	2.29	Approaching
2. Performs simple, routine errands like:	2.50	Approaching
2.1 Buy biscuit	2.38	Approaching
2.2 Get a glass of water	3.00	Developing
2.3 Get a spoon	3.56	Mastered
2.4 Get a plate	3.56	Mastered
Others: please specify (turn on/off TV) p7	4.00	Mastered
3. Demonstrates how to follow orders or requests by:		
3.1 waiting for one’s turn	2.67	Developing
3.2 listening attentively when somebody is talking	2.56	Developing
3.3 forming a line when passing in and out of the room	2.22	Approaching
4. Seeks more autonomy	1.89	Approaching

5. Carries out one daily chore with a reminder (e.g. water the plants)	2.44	Approaching
6. Terminates inappropriate behavior with one reminder	1.89	Approaching
Totality	2.69	Developing

As illustrated in Table 10, it comes out that performs simple, routine errands like buy biscuits, get a glass of water, get a spoon, get a plate and turn on and off the television garners the highest weighted of 3.30, demonstrates how to follow orders or requests by waiting for one's turn, listening attentively when somebody is talking and forming a line when passing in and out of the room followed with an average mean of 2.48, and seeks more autonomy and terminates inappropriate behavior with one reminder take similar weighted mean of 1.89 is the last rank.

Moreover, Table 10 reveals that children with autism are at the **developing level** as far as self at work competencies obtaining weighted of mean 2.69. This means that children have executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting.

This is supported by Hume (2016) when she said that reaching the maximum level of independence is a priority for all children with autism because this is the key to successful community. Thus, it is an accomplishment to children with special needs when they begin to complete tasks with minimal adult prompting and guidance.

Autism Awareness Australia (2023) underscores the importance of fostering independence in children with autism, highlighting that achieving self-sufficiency enhances personal well-being and promotes community engagement and future employability. The article emphasizes that incorporating independence skills into daily life at home, school, and in the community enables faster skill-building and increased confidence in children.

TABLE XI: Listening or Receptive Language Skills

E. Listening/ Receptive Language Skills	WM	Description
1. Follows one-step instructions:		
1.1 Sit down	3.78	Mastered
1.2 Stand Up	3.78	Mastered
1.3 Come here	3.11	Developing
1.4 Put hands down	3.11	Developing
1.5 Wave bye-bye	3.44	Mastered
1.6 Give me a hug	3.33	Mastered
1.7 Puts arms up	3.44	Mastered
1.8 Clap your hands	3.67	Mastered
1.9 Turn around	3.22	Developing
1.10 Jump	3.44	Mastered
1.11 Give me a kiss	3.44	Mastered
1.12 Throw this away	3.33	Mastered
1.13 Close the door	3.44	Mastered
1.14 Blow a kiss	3.33	Mastered
1.15 Turn on the light	3.44	Mastered
1.16 Get a tissue	3.33	Mastered
1.17 Turn on the music	3.67	Mastered
1.18 Put on the shelf	3.22	Developing
1.19 Give me five	3.44	Mastered
1.20 Stomp your feet	3.33	Mastered
1.21 Inhale	3.44	Mastered
1.22 Exhale	3.44	Mastered

1.23 Blow a candle	3.44	Mastered
1.24 Blow bubbles	3.33	Mastered
1.25 Open mouth wide	3.33	Mastered
1.26 Close mouth	3.44	Mastered
1.27 Stick out tongue	3.33	Mastered
1.28 Move tongue and own/left and right	3.11	Developing
1.29 Laugh	3.22	Developing
1.30 Giggle	3.00	Developing
1.31 Wear your slippers	3.44	Mastered
Totality	3.38	Mastered

As presented in Table 11, children with autism follow one-step instructions which sit down and stand up rank first with weighted of 3.78, followed by clap your hands and turn on the music with 3.67, Wave bye-bye, puts arms up, jump, give me a kiss, close the door, turn on the light, give me five, inhale, exhale, blow a candle, close your mouth and wear your slippers with similar weighted mean of 3.44. Another instructions like give me a hug, throw this away, blow a kiss, get a tissue, stomp your feet, blow bubbles, open mouth wide and stick out tongue bring together the same weighted mean of 3.33, turn around, put on the shelf, and laugh collect weighted of 2.22, come here, put hands down and move tongue and down/left and right obtain weighted mean of 3.11 while giggle gets the lowest weighted mean of 3.00.

Totality of its weighted mean is 3.38 which mean the children with autism **mastered** the competencies by executing or performing the given social activities without prodding and prompting. According to Madaule (2007), listening does not necessarily mean obeying. He further explained that if a child knows or chooses what to listen and what not to listen to is tantamount to good listener. He added that listening is at the origin of the child's focal point and attention span as it is a vital component in the child's impulsive engagement and inspiration.

For Brown and Elder (2014) when allowing children with special needs to communicate, the most important factor is to give them ample time to process the message used in the conversation and formulate responses accordingly. Children with Autism attain mastery with regards to listening and receptive skills if speakers slow down the utterances of their speeches and look directly at the child's eyes with a low-tone voice.

TABLE XII: Expressive Language Skills

<i>F. Expressive Language Skills</i>	WM	Description
1. Points to desired items in response to "What do you want?"	2.78	Developing
2.Points to desired items spontaneously	3.00	Developing
3. Puts 2 words together	2.44	Approaching
4.Can name objects like:		
4.1 ball	3.22	Developing
4.2 cell phone	2.56	Developing
4.3 pencil	2.67	Developing
5.Can labels pictures		
5.1 subject's own picture	2.33	Approaching
5.2 subject's father or mother	2.44	Approaching
Others: please specify: guardian	2.00	Approaching
6.Verbally request desired items	2.38	Approaching
7.States or gestures yes or no for preferred and non-preferred items	2.44	Approaching

8.Labels familiar people like father, mother, sister, brother or guardian	2.00	Approaching
9.Makes a choice between ball or doll	3.22	Developing
10.Reciprocates greetings like:		
10.1 Good morning!	2.78	Developing
10.2 Hi! Hello!	2.67	Developing
10.3 Thank you!	2.88	Developing
11.Answers social questions like:		
11.1 Do you want to eat?	2.56	Developing
11.2 Do you want to go home?	2.56	Developing
12.Recites common nursery rhymes and ingles with the teacher	2.00	Approaching
13.Imitates two-and three-word phrases	3.00	Developing
14.Calls parent from a distance	2.44	Approaching
15.Uses simple sentences		
It's a	1.89	Approaching
I see a	1.89	Approaching
I have a	1.89	Approaching
Totality	2.50	Approaching

Table 12 reveals that children with autism make a choice between ball or doll with weighted mean of 3.22 and the subject who uses simple sentences garners the lowest collective weighted mean of 1.89.

Totality of its weighted mean is 2.50 which imply that children with autism with regards to expressive language skills are still at the **approaching level** of competencies. This signifies the subject has occasionally executed or performed the given social activities with or without prodding.

According to Foegen and Resan (2009) when they said that child's verbal language may be absent or present, or lacks of the usual communication form thus evaluation of these competencies should be administered.

Furthermore, the Autism Speaks (2012) explained that children with autism have word retrieval issues. A special child may know the answers of the questions being asked for but he or she may not be able to come up with the words. Thus, reprimanding the child for not listening and responding is not commendable.

TABLE XIII: AUDITORY RECEPTION

G. Auditory Perception	WM	Description
1.Auditory Acuity		
1.1 listens to body sounds such as:		
1.1.1 humming	2.89	Developing
1.1.2 kissing	3.11	Developing
1.1.3 cough	2.67	Developing
1.1.4 giggling	3.00	Developing
1.1.5 crying	3.11	Developing
1.1.6 shouting	2.67	Developing
1.1.7 sneezing	2.22	Approaching
1.1.8 yawning	2.67	Developing
1.1.9 checking tongue	2.11	Approaching
1.1.10 finger tapping	2.56	Developing
1.1.11 whistling	1.67	No Notation
1.1.12 whispering	2.11	Approaching

Others: please specify		
1.2 responds functionally to household sounds, musical instruments, animal sounds, common toy sounds, school sounds	3.00	Developing
1.3 initiates single verbalizations of what was whispered or verbalized	2.44	Approaching
1.4 repeats what was instructed such as tap on desk, cough, laugh, clap, etc.	2.44	Approaching
Totality	2.80	Developing

Table 13 discloses the results of the auditory acuity which states that responds functionally to household sounds, musical instruments, animal sounds, common toy sounds, school ranks first with weighted mean of 3.00, listens to body sounds such as humming, kissing, cough, giggling, crying, shouting, sneezing, yawning, checking tongue, finger tapping, whistling and whispering ranks second with collective weighted mean of 2.56, and initiates single verbalizations of what was whispered or verbalized and repeats what was instructed such as tap on desk, cough, laugh, clap, and others ranks last with an analogous weighted mean of 2.44.

Totality of its weighted mean equivalent to 2.79 signifies **developing level** of competencies as far as auditory perception is concerned. This tells further that children with autism have executed or performed the given social activities without prodding and prompting. This fact is supported of Larocci et al (2010) statement that children with Autism showed less visual influence and more auditory influence on their bimodal speech perception.

C. Relationship Between Socioeconomic Status and Social Interaction and Communication Competencies of the Children with Autism

The parent's socioeconomic status establishes relationship with social communication and interaction competencies of children with autism. The socioeconomic status under study included parents' educational attainment, availability of reading materials at home and family financial status. The relationship between the variables is computed using Chi-square of Independent Samples by presenting the chi-square value and critical chi-square value. Decision and interpretation are also shown.

TABLE XIV: Relationship between Socioeconomic Status and Social Communication and Interaction Skills of Children with Autism

COMPENTENCIES versus	Chi-square value	Critical chi-square value	Decision	Interpretation
Parents Educational Attainment	18.65	25.00	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Availability of Reading Materials at Home	28.8	36.42	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Family Financial Status	4.13	21.03	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Totality	51.58	82.45	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 14 shows that there is no significant relationship between socioeconomic status and the social interaction and communication competencies of the children with ASD. It illustrates that the critical tabled chi-square is greater than the computed chi-square. The result displays that there is no enough evidence to show that the socioeconomic status has bearing on the children's competencies. Therefore, the above posted data affirmed the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the socioeconomic status and the social interaction and communication competencies of the children with autism.

This study agrees with the findings of the research conducted by Sun et al (2014) which focused about the parental concerns, socioeconomic status, and the risk of autism. Results of the said research established a no significant relationship between ASD and SES.

Verdicts of this investigation as reflected in Table 15 can be associated with the study initiated by the American Sociological Association dated April 4, 2011. In the said article Peter Bearman, Cole Professor of the Social Sciences at Columbia

University, mentioned that children in the low-income families who are living in poor neighbourhood are likely have less understanding of the developmental dynamics. Bearman added that in wealthier localities, there are more opportunities for parents and children with autism to socialize at the parks, schools and other pivotal areas wherein social interaction and communication activities are richer.

Social communication and interaction skills of the children with autism can be strengthened or weakened depending on how people around them support their needs and extend unconditional love for them. Thus, to be their teacher, one must be a learner and a learner forever. One has to get to know the children whom a teacher is intended to teach. In this manner, whether the children with ASD belong to a wealthier family or a poorer family, they will enjoy and attain the same level of development as far as social interaction and communication competencies are concerned.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the social communication and interaction competencies of the children with autism are not related with the socioeconomic status of the family. Through the findings and based on the given result, most parents' have income ranges from Php 7,000.00 and below. It is very evident that their parents have limited financial resources to defray the expenses incurred for the needs of the children with Autism. Exposure to socially richer environment, for example, is commendable for the children to have an aesthetic learning experience. Due to financial constraints, this outside home exploration can be forgone.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bon, M. ,2002. Restructured Basic Education Curriculum. Distributed by the Teachers' Relief.
- [2] Dañocup, O. B., 2010. Classroom Management: Preparing Special Education Teachers. Lorimar Publishing, Inc. 776 Aurora Blvd. cor. Boston Street, Cubao, Quezon City, Metro Manila
- [3] Frost, L. et.al, 2010. The Picture Exchange Communication System Training Manual. Published in 2002 in the United States by Pyramid Educational Consultants, Inc. 13 Garfield Way, Newark, DE 19713: Reprinted 2010
- [4] Hallahan, D. et.al., 2012. Exceptional Learners: An Introduction to Special Education. Twelfth Edition, 2012.Upper Saddle River, New Jersey
- [5] Jacob, M., 1998. Understanding the Nature of an Autistic Child.1st Edition, 1998; JMJ Books, Cebu City
- [6] Jeffree, D. et.al, 1993. Teaching the Handicapped Child. Souvenir Press (Educational and Academic) Ltd, 43 Great Russell Street, London WC1B 3PA and Printed in Great Britain by Redwood Press Limited, Meldstan, Wiltshire
- [7] Adrienne Warber, 2015. Teaching Techniques for Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder. (http://autism.lovetoknow.com/Teaching_Methods_for_Autistic_Children)
- [8] Chaban, Peter, 2010. Special education: Are regular classrooms enough? (<http://www.aboutkidshealth.ca/en/news/columns/education/pages/special-education-are-regular-classrooms-enough.aspx>)
- [9] Dana Lee Baker, Laurie A. Drapela. Mostly the mother: Concentration of adverse employment effects on mothers of children with autism. The Social Science Journal, 2010; DOI: 10.1016/j.soscij.2010.01.013 <http://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2010/06/100623085725.htm>
- [10] Division of Birth Defects, National Center on Birth Defects and Developmental Disabilities, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, August 12, 2015. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD):Treatment(<http://www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/treatment.html>)
- [11] Doheny, K. et.al., 2011. Child with Autism May Affect Family Income: Study Shows Mothers of Autistic Children Are Less Likely to Be Employed (<http://www.webmd.com/brain/autism/news/20110511/child-with-autism-may-affect-family-income?page=2>).
- [12] Elsevier, 2014, Parental concerns, socioeconomic status, and the risk of autism spectrum conditions in a population-based study <http://dx.oj.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2014.07.037>
- [13] ETS Policy Statement for Documentation of Autism Spectrum Disorder in Adolescents and Adults, 2013, Office of Disability Policy Educational Testing Service Princeton, NJ 08541

- [14] Hesch, K, 2015. 7 Activities to Develop Receptive Language. North Shore Pediatric Therapy <http://nspt4kids.com/parenting/7-activities-develop-receptive-language/>
- [15] Increase Autism Awareness and the Early Signs of ASD. CB# 7180 UNC-Chapel Hill Chapel Hill, NC 27599 (<http://www.teacch.com/news/join-us-in-broadening-autism-awareness>).
- [16] Jaymalin, M, April 10, 2014 - Number of People with Autism increasing <http://www.philstar.com/headlines/2014/04/10/1310840/number-people-autism-increasing>)
- [17] Larocci, Grace et al, 2013 Visual influences on speech perception in children with autism. <http://aut.sagepub.com/content/14/4/305.abstract>
- [18] Lauren Lowry, Can children with language impairments learn two languages?
- [19] Kohnert, K., Yim, D., Nett, K., Kan, P. F., & Duran, L. (2005). Intervention with linguistically diverse preschool children: A focus on developing home languages(s). *Language, Speech and Hearing Services in Schools*. 36, 251-263. (<http://www.hanen.org/Helpful-Info/Articles/Can-children-with-language-impairments-learn-two-l.aspx>)
- [20] Madaule, Paul.2007. Power of Listening. The Magazine for Montessori Families. <http://www.listeningfitness.com/PDF/PowerofListening.pdf>
- [21] Raising Children Network, 2006-2016. Play for Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder. http://raisingchildren.net.au/articles/autism_spectrum_disorder_play.html.
- [22] Simon Baron-Cohen, 2009, Autism: The Empathizing–Systemizing (E-S) Theory, *The Year in Cognitive Neuroscience 2009: Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.* 1156: 68–80 (2009); doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.2009.04467.x C 2009 New York Academy of Sciences http://www.autismtruths.org/pdf/Autism-The%20emphathizing- systemizing%20es%20theory_SBC_ARC.pdf)
- [23] Sen. Trillanes IV, July 22, 2013, An act creating “Philippine Commission on Autism Spectrum Disorders and the Office of Autism Services”, (<http://www.senate.gov.ph/lisdata/1702614243!.pdf>)